

STRENGTHENING CLINICAL TRIAL REGULATORY AND ETHICAL REVIEW OVERSIGHT IN EAST AFRICA.

D1.4: Data Management Plan

Project acronym: ACCESSAFRICA 2

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ABSTRACT:	This report presents the initial version of the data management plan for the ACCESSAFRICA 2 project. It summarizes the various data types that will be collected for the project and outlines how FAIR principles will be applied within ACCESSAFRICA 2.
Keyword List:	Data, DMP, FAIR, protection, best practices, open science, regulations

Consortium:

	ROLE	NAME	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	University of Oslo	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	Uganda National Health Research Organization	UNHRO	Uganda
3.	Partner	Jimma University	JU	Ethiopia
4.	Partner	Uganda National Council for Science and Technology	UNCST	Uganda
5.	Partner	National Drug Authority	NDA	Uganda

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1 Data Summary

The main goal of ACCESSAFRICA 2 is to improve ethical review and regulatory capacity for clinical trials in two sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries, with specific focus on the review and oversight of reported adverse events during clinical trials, improve efficiencies of the National Ethics Committee (NECs) and National Regulatory Agencies (NRAs), and equip them with skills and knowledge for improved operations during outbreaks and epidemics.

To accomplish this goal, ACCESSAFRICA 2 relies into three specific objectives—including,

- a. Increasing the regulatory and ethics capacity of NRAs, NECs, and IRBs for review, approval, and oversight of clinical trials in Ethiopia and Uganda.
- b. Strengthening links between ethics and regulatory functions by establishing collaborative relationships between National Ethics Committee (NEC), National Regulatory Agencies (NRA) and local IRB, and communication among the related actors.
- c. Build capacity for increased research leadership through collaboration with the Eastern Africa Consortium for Clinical Research (EACCR).

Based on the project objectives, the time-bound and measurable outputs will include the following:

- Staff training reports in pharmacovigilance and clinical trial regulatory mechanisms.
- RA officers and REC members training in review and oversight of vaccine development studies.
- Development of a safety monitoring system to track trends in safety reporting.
- Report on joint inspections of clinical trials sites.
- A report from desk review of RAs and IRBs
- Guidelines for joint review of clinical trials in Uganda
- Framework for joint review of clinical trial in Ethiopia
- Peer review articles from COVID 19 survey
- Evaluation reports of clinical trial applications
- A clinical trial operational manual

- A training manual on research leadership
- A manual to build capacity for regulatory authorities and ethics committees in post-trial access on investigation drug products.
- A training manual on ethics review capacity
- Report on COVID 19 survey
- Joint review guideline and framework for Ethiopia
- Effect collaboration between Clinical trial and Ethics regulatory bodies
- Improved regulatory and ethic review processes for clinical trials

2 Project Data

Some ACCESSAFRICA 2 outputs will necessitate data collection, which will involve gathering data in various formats—including interview data, text transcripts, quantitative data, qualitative data, data from reviews of documentation, training sessions, stakeholder consultation, inspections and workshops.

The data types to be collected by ACCESSAFRICA 2 are diverse.

- Data from the review of documentation
- Personal data from interviews and survey
- Personal data from stakeholder consultation meetings, workshops and inspections—including expert stakeholders.
- Other data from training materials and guidelines

This serves as the project's initial Data Management Plan (DMP), which will be subject to periodic updates. Future revisions will incorporate additional technical details, including data file sizes and the actual data formats generated.

ACCESSAFRICA 2 plans to conduct stakeholder meetings, training workshops, and joint inspections of clinical trial sites. The level of participation from stakeholders, trainees and inspectors is expected to vary, depending on their specific needs and availability. ACCESSAFRICA 2 will utilize training sessions organized in collaboration with partner institutions to collect data on learning processes and outcomes.

The ACCESSAFRICA 2 Work Packages will utilize all the data gathered for the purposes specified in the ACCESSAFRICA 2 Description of Action. ACCESSAFRICA 2 will also rigorously adhere to the FAIR principles and data protection regulations.

To allow for the needed flexibility of ACCESSAFRICA 2 partners in gathering and storing data, data will be curated by the partner institution mainly responsible for the relevant tasks, on the condition that the repository is GDPR-compliant. The partner institution is responsible for ensuring this.

3 FAIR Data

In light of the nature of ACCESSAFRICA 2, where a significant amount of data or research knowledge is anticipated to be generated, the project will align with the principles of freely and openly exchanging data and knowledge, along with open-access publishing. The openness of the data will adhere to the Guidelines of the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020, as well as the Commission Recommendation in 2018 on access to and preservation of scientific information.

The data generated will follow the principles of being "Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable" (FAIR). Data will be made as open as possible while respecting necessary restrictions, and it will be archived by partner institutions responsible for its management. Unless restricted by privacy, confidentiality considerations, and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requirements, data will also be published in FAIR data repositories, such as Zenodo, following a thorough data curation process. Zenodo and similar repositories utilize metadata schemas to create machine-actionable metadata that can be indexed by various search engines, including Google Dataset Search. By adhering to these standards,

data will be thoroughly described with extensive metadata to enhance its FAIRness (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Digital items will be assigned a DataCite DOI upon publication, and they can be accessed via their identifier using the secure and standard communication protocol HTTPS. Data subject to an embargo can also be shared through a DOI or a private link, allowing external partners, such as reviewers of journal articles, to access it.

Metadata elements that contribute to FAIRness encompass the research project's title, author and co-author names, data descriptions, a research abstract summarizing the study, funding details (including grant project name, acronym, and number), publication date, version number, research discipline categories, data-defining keywords, Digital Object Identifier (DOI), licensing information (such as Creative Commons), a title and link to associated publications, and links to references or related content.

By incorporating these metadata elements, data becomes searchable and discoverable, accessible to other potential users, and ensures transparency regarding its reuse. Additionally, a human-readable ReadMe file, comprehensively discussing the digital item being archived, is a mandatory document in the data curation process. Data generated by the project will be made publicly available upon its completion, following a CC-BY license, unless conditions specified in the Grant Agreement dictate otherwise.

4 Other Research Outputs

The research outputs of the project are governed by the Grant Agreement. In alignment with the principles of Open Science, scientific articles will be published in open-access journals, and project data will be archived as previously described. This approach ensures that the research outputs of the project are readily accessible and available for reuse by a diverse range of potential users, including clinical trials regulators, research ethics committees, researchers, educators, policymakers, and the general public.

Given that the project is currently in its initial phase and that valuable research outputs may emerge as the project progresses, this section will also be updated in the subsequent Data Management Plans (DMPs).

5 Data Security

During the project's timeframe, data will be securely stored in full compliance with GDPR regulations. Individual institutions will gather and manage the data generated in ACCESSAFRICA 2 according to their respective regulatory specifications. However, each partner institution will retain a copy of the data based on the data sharing and data transferring agreements of each partner institution. For data sharing, the EACCR has developed a data management and sharing plan for its partners, and this will be adopted for the project. The data will be stored for up to ten years after the end of the project. The shared data will be stored in accordance with the data regulations of the receiving institution. For example, the University of Oslo offers a local network for storing project data, and access is strictly restricted to project members. This storage solution has been authorized to handle Red (Confidential/Sensitive) data according to the Norwegian classification system. UNHRO/UVRI has a secure server that is encrypted with limited access.

6 Data protection and anonymization

- Personal data will be processed quantitatively and qualitatively, and transcriptions may be necessary in some cases.
- Audio files requiring anonymization during transcription will have the audio and files deleted after verification.
- Data will be anonymized unless participants provide consent or in cases where anonymization is not expected, such as during stakeholder consultation events.
- The project will not maintain a link between anonymized data and identifying participant data.
- All data analysis will exclusively use anonymized data.
- Only anonymized data will be deposited in data repositories at the project's conclusion.

- Research participants will be required to grant explicit consent for data deposition in a repository as part of the informed consent process before data collection.

7 Sharing of results

The rights for disseminating and exploiting the intellectual property and know-how will be addressed through a data-sharing agreement, which all partners of ACCESSAFRICA 2 will sign. The guidelines jointly developed within this project will be made available to enhance research ethics capacity and research leadership across Sub-Saharan Africa.